

THE EFFECT OF WORK MOTIVATION, WORK DISCIPLINE, AND JOB SATISFACTION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT AGHARA COFFEE ROASTER

Novita Br. Simanjuntak¹, Ewi Br. Sihombing², Galli Kurnia Dinda³, Lenta Friska Purba^{4*}, Yan Raja David Hamonangan Damanik⁵

¹Faculty of Economics and Business / Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan

²Faculty of Economics and Business / Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan

³Faculty of Economics and Business / Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan

^{4*}Faculty of Economics and Business / Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, PUI
PT Human Resource Management Research And Inovation Center, Indonesia

⁵Faculty of Economics and Business / STIE Pangeran Antasari, Medan

E-mail: novitasmjtk11@gmail.com^{1*}, ewiangelina2607@gmail.com², gallikurniad@gmail.com³,
lentapurba@unprimdn.ac.id⁴, yr.damanik@gmail.com⁵

Received : 10 March 2026

Accepted : 01 April 2026

Revised : 15 March 2026

Published : 30 April 2026

Abstract

This study aims to determine and analyze the influence of work motivation, work discipline and job satisfaction on employee performance at *Aghara Coffee Roaster*. This type of research uses quantitative research. The research sample was 30 respondents. The data analysis method used multiple linear regression analysis. Based on the results of the t hypothesis test, it can be concluded that work motivation has a significant effect on employee performance with a calculated t_{value} of $3.797 > t_{\text{table}} 2.055$ and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, work discipline has a significant effect on employee performance with a calculated t_{value} of $2.303 > t_{\text{table}} 2.055$ and a significance value of $0.030 < 0.05$ and job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance with a calculated t_{value} of $3.341 > t_{\text{table}} 2.055$ and a significance value of $0.003 < 0.05$. Based on the results of the F hypothesis test, it can be concluded that simultaneously/together work motivation, work discipline and job satisfaction have an effect on employee performance with an F_{count} value of $28.508 > F_{\text{table}} 2.975$ and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on the analysis of the coefficient of determination, the coefficient of determination or Adjusted R-Square value of 0.740 or 74% of work motivation, work discipline and job satisfaction has an effect on employee performance, while 26% is the influence of other variables that did not participate in this study.

Keywords: *Work Motivation, Work Discipline, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

Coffee is a beverage widely consumed by people around the world. The caffeine content in coffee makes it popular because it can increase energy, reduce fatigue, and help people stay focused. The development of the coffee industry has encouraged the emergence of various coffee shops, making it a highly attractive business sector for entrepreneurs. One such business is *Aghara Coffee Roaster*. *Aghara Coffee Roaster* operates as a coffee distributor focused on product quality and prompt service. Located in Medan, *Aghara Coffee Roaster* is known for its ability to meet customer demand in a timely manner, both through expedition delivery and direct sales. *Aghara Coffee Roaster* also offers various coffee varieties, including Arabica and Robusta, and has a slow bar, a comfortable place to hang out and enjoy a cup of coffee. Therefore, employee performance is crucial to support the future sustainability of the industry. Employee performance is the result of work achieved in carrying out tasks in accordance with Company standards, both in terms of quality, quantity, and timeliness. Optimal performance will contribute to the achievement of goals and increase the Company's competitiveness. However, at *Aghara Coffee Roaster*, challenges remain. Some employees use their mobile phones during work hours, resulting in suboptimal discipline and focus. Work motivation is an internal drive that fuels enthusiasm and passion to achieve set goals. Work motivation at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* plays a crucial role in the distribution chain. High motivation is expected to increase productivity and support the coffee industry in meeting market demand. Work discipline plays a crucial role in

THE EFFECT OF WORK MOTIVATION, WORK DISCIPLINE, AND JOB SATISFACTION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT AGHARA COFFEE ROASTER

Simanjuntak, et al

supporting employee performance. It helps employees adhere to rules, procedures, and responsibilities. However, at *Aghara Coffee Roaster*, some employees still need to improve their time management to optimize the distribution process. Good discipline will impact the efficiency and effectiveness of company operations. Job satisfaction is an employee's positive feelings about their job and the work environment. In the business world, maintaining job satisfaction is as important as attracting new customers. Job satisfaction arises when customers are satisfied with the results of our work. A high level of job satisfaction not only drives employee loyalty but also increases employee enthusiasm for work. Based on the background outlined above, this study was conducted with the title "The Effect of Work Motivation, Work Discipline, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* in Medan City".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Motivation

According to Hamali (2016:131), "Motivation is defined as a person's desire and energy directed toward achieving a goal". According to Busro (2018:65), "There are several indicators of work motivation, including: the need for achievement, the need for affiliation, the need for power".

Work Discipline

According to Hamali (2016:213), "Discipline is a management activity to implement organizational standards". According to Sinambela & Sinambela (2019:356), "Indicators of work discipline: frequency of attendance, level of alertness, adherence to work standards, adherence to regulations, work ethic".

Job Satisfaction

According to Busro (2018), "Job satisfaction is a state in which a person feels content, relieved, and happy because the work situation and conditions can fulfill their needs, desires, and expectations". According to Afandi (2018:82), "The indicators of job satisfaction include: work, wages, promotions, supervisors, coworkers".

Employee Performance

According to Afandi (2018:84), "Performance is the results achieved by a person according to the applicable standards for the job in question". According to Afandi (2018:89), there are performance indicators, including: Work results, Work behavior, Personal characteristics".

Framework Of Thinking

In summary, the framework of thinking used in this research is described as follows:

METHOD

The type of research conducted in this study is quantitative research. In this research, the researcher used primary and secondary data as data sources. This research was conducted at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* located in Ruko Abadi Palace, Jl. Abadi Block A1, Tanjung, Rejo, Medan Sunggal District, Medan City, North Sumatra 20122. The research period was from June 2025 to October 2025. This research was carried out from September 2025 to February 2026. The research population at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* was 30 people. The sampling method used in this study is saturated sampling or total sampling, which is a sampling technique where all members of the population are used as samples. Thus, the number of samples taken was 30 respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work Motivation	30	12	30	24.17	5.621
Work Dicipline	30	10	50	42.33	7.756
Job Satisfaction	30	10	50	42.20	8.130
Employee Performance	30	12	30	25.73	4.008
Valid N (listwise)	30				

1. Of the 30 samples collected, work motivation data showed a minimum score of 12 and a maximum score of 30. The average was 24.17 with a deviation of 5.621.
2. Of the 30 samples collected, work discipline data showed a minimum score of 10 and a maximum score of 50. The average was 42.33 with a deviation of 7.756.
3. Of the 30 samples collected, job satisfaction data showed a minimum score of 10 and a maximum score of 50. The average was 42.20 with a deviation of 8.130.
4. Of the 30 samples collected, employee performance data showed a minimum score of 12 and a maximum score of 30. The average was 25.73 with a deviation of 4.008.

Table 2. Normality Test

<i>One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test</i>		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		30
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.93522941
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.071
	Positive	.062
	Negative	-.071
Test Statistic		.071
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.		

Table 2 shows the probability value p or *Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)* of 0.200. Because the probability value p, which is 0.200, is greater than the significance level, which is 0.05. This means the data is normally distributed.

Figure 1. Normality Test–Normal Probability Plots

Figure 1 above is a normality test using a normal probability plot approach, while in Figure 2 above is a normality test using a histogram approach. As seen in Figure 1, the dots spread around the diagonal line.

Figure 2. Normality Test–Histogram

Meanwhile in Figure 2, you can see that the curve is a normal curve, namely bell-shaped and in the middle, so the data is said to be normally distributed.

Table 3. Multicollinearity

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Work Motivation	0.973	1.028
	Work Dicipline	0.449	2.229
	Job Satisfaction	0.454	2.202

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

THE EFFECT OF WORK MOTIVATION, WORK DISCIPLINE, AND JOB SATISFACTION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT AGHARA COFFEE ROASTER

Simanjuntak, et al

Table 3 above shows the VIF value is below 10 and the Tolerance value is not < 0.1, this means that among the independent variables in this study there is no relationship or no relationship with each other, so it can be concluded that the regression model does not contain multicollinearity.

Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.561	2.561			
	Work Motivation	0.260	0.068	0.365	0.973	1.028
	Work Dicipline	0.168	0.073	0.326	0.449	2.229
	Job Satisfaction	0.231	0.069	0.469	0.454	2.202

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test via the *Glejser* test in Table 4, it can be seen that Sig. each variable has a value of more than 0.05 and it can be said that this shows that heteroscedasticity does not occur in the regression model in this study. and the independent variables can be stated as not experiencing heteroscedasticity.

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.561	2.561		1.000	0.327
	Work Motivation	0.260	0.068	0.365	3.797	0.001
	Work Dicipline	0.168	0.073	0.326	2.303	0.030
	Job Satisfaction	0.231	0.069	0.469	3.341	0.003

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Table 5 Above it can be seen that the multiple linear regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$Y = 2,561 + 0,260X_1 + 0,168X_2 + 0,231X_3 + 0,5$$

Based on this equation it can be interpreted as follows:

1. The table above shows a constant value of 2.561, indicating that if the variables for work motivation, work discipline, and job satisfaction are 0, then the employee performance level is 2.561.
2. The table above shows that the variable for work motivation has a significant effect on employee performance of 0.260, indicating that changes in the variable for work motivation affect employee performance by 0.260 units.
3. The information above shows that the variable for work discipline affects employee performance by 0.168 units, indicating that changes in the variable for work discipline affect employee performance by 0.168 units.
4. The information above shows that the variable for job satisfaction affects employee performance by 0.231 units, indicating that changes in the variable for job satisfaction affect employee performance by 0.231 units.

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing - F

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	357.258	3	119.086	28.508	0.000
	Residual	108.608	26	4.177		
	Total	465.867	29			

THE EFFECT OF WORK MOTIVATION, WORK DISCIPLINE, AND JOB SATISFACTION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT AGHARA COFFEE ROASTER

Simanjuntak, et al

The information above displays the results of the simultaneous F test. Based on the test results, the calculated F_{value} is $28.508 > F_{\text{table}} 2.975$. From the results, it can be concluded that the study accepts H_4 . Therefore, it can be concluded that all independent variables included in this study have an effect on employee performance..

Table 7. Hypothesis Testing - T

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	2.561	2.561		1.000	0.327
	Work Motivation	0.260	0.068	0.365	3.797	0.001
	Work Dicipline	0.168	0.073	0.326	2.303	0.030
	Job Satisfaction	0.231	0.069	0.469	3.341	0.003

a. *Dependent Variable:* Employee Performance

Table 7 above that the results obtained:

1. Testing the First Hypothesis (H_1)
A significant correlation between motivation and employee performance was found at $0.000 < 0.05$. This is supported by a calculated t_{value} of $3.797 > t_{\text{table}}$ of 2.055 . This indicates that work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee performance.
2. Testing the Second Hypothesis (H_2)
A significant correlation between work discipline and employee performance was found at $0.030 < 0.05$. This is supported by a calculated t_{value} of $2.055 > t_{\text{table}}$ of 2.055 . This indicates that work discipline has a positive and significant influence on employee performance.
3. Testing the Third Hypothesis (H_3)
A significant correlation between job satisfaction and employee performance was found at $0.003 < 0.05$. This is supported by a calculated t_{value} of $3.341 > t_{\text{table}}$ of 2.055 . This indicates that competence has a positive and significant influence on the dependent variable on employee performance.

Table 9. Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.876 ^a	0.767	0.740	2.044

The table above displays the results of the coefficient of determination test, which shows a coefficient of determination of 0.740. This means that work motivation, work discipline, and job satisfaction influence employee performance by 74%. Meanwhile, the remaining 26% of the coefficient of determination can be explained by other factors not included in the study, such as leadership style, work environment, salary, incentives, and so on.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

Work motivation is the drive and enthusiasm within employees to achieve specific goals. A significant correlation between work motivation and employee performance was found at $0.000 < 0.05$. This is supported by the calculated t_{value} of $3.797 > t_{\text{table}} 2.055$. This indicates that motivation has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. These findings align with previous research by Ulya & Mutiarahmah (2025), which demonstrated that motivation has a positive and direct impact on employee performance.

The Influence of Work Discipline on Employee Performance

Work discipline is the attitude of obedience and adherence to established rules or values, carried out consciously and without coercion to achieve goals. A significant effect of discipline on employee performance was found at $0.030 < 0.05$. This is supported by the calculated t_{value} of $2.303 > t_{\text{table}}$ of 2.055 . This indicates that work discipline has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. This finding aligns with previous research by Musdalifah *et al.* (2025) on discipline, namely that the discipline variable significantly influences employee performance.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is enjoyable and enjoyable for one's job. This attitude is reflected in work morale, discipline, and work performance. This satisfaction is experienced within work, outside of work, and a combination of both. A significant correlation between competency and employee performance was found at $0.003 < 0.05$. This is supported by the calculated t_{value} of $3.341 > t_{\text{table}}$ of 2.055 . This indicates that job satisfaction significantly impacts employee performance. This finding aligns with previous research by Ramadan & Endriastuty (2025). The results of this study indicate that job satisfaction significantly influences employee performance.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the study on "The Influence of Work Motivation, Work Discipline, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* in Medan," the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Work motivation influences employee performance by $0.000 < 0.05$. This is supported by the calculated t_{test} of $3.797 > t_{\text{table}}$ of 2.055 . Therefore, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This indicates that work motivation positively and significantly influences employee performance at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* in Medan. It can be concluded that H_1 is accepted.
2. Work discipline influences employee performance by $0.030 < 0.05$. This is supported by the calculated t_{test} of $2.303 > t_{\text{table}}$ of 2.055 . This indicates that work discipline positively and significantly influences employee performance at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* in Medan. It can be concluded that H_2 is accepted.
3. Job satisfaction influences employee performance by $0.003 < 0.05$. Supported by the calculated t_{value} of $3.011 > t_{\text{table}}$ 2.055 , job satisfaction positively and significantly influences employee performance at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* Medan. It can be concluded that H_3 is accepted.
4. Based on the calculated F_{value} of $28.508 > F_{\text{table}}$ 2.975 , the results can be concluded that the study accepts H_4 . Therefore, it can be concluded that all independent variables included in this study influence employee performance at *Aghara Coffee Roaster* Medan.

REFERENCES

- Arif Yusuf Hamali, S.S., M. M. (2016). *Pemahaman Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia* (1st ed.). CAPS (Center for Academic Publishing Service).
- Busro, D. M. (2018). *Teori-Teori Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia* (1st Ed.). KENCANA.
- Ghozali, I. (2016). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IBM SPSS Edisi 9* (9th ed.). Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro,.
- Musdalifah, N., Jaya, S., & Bebas, A. R. (2025). *Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Peningkatan Kinerja Pegawai Pada Kantor Kecamatan Biringkanaya Kota Makassar*. 1–11.
- Prof.Dr. Pandi Afandi, SE, M. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia; Teori, Konsep Dan Indikator* (1st ed.). Nusa Media Yogyakarta.
- Ramadan, T. A. R., & Endriastuty, Y. (2025). *Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan*. Indonesian Journal of Management Science, 4(2 SE-Articles), 129–136.
- Sinambela, L. P., & Sinambela, S. (2019). *Manajemen Kinerja*. Rajawali Pers.
- Sugiyono. (2016). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif Dan R&D*. Alfa Beta
- Ulya, N., & Mutiarahmah, A. (2025). *Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Di Laznas Dewan Dakwah Islamiyah Indonesia Jawa Barat*. 16, 63–69.